

Complex Treatment of Acute Paraproctitis against the Background of Diabetes

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Abstract: *Due to slow microcirculation in patients with acute paraproctitis diabetes, the wound is cleared of purulent-necrotic tissues and regeneration is slow, and general intoxication is observed. Patients were divided into 2 main and control groups. Patients were treated with standard - daily local antiseptics and received antibiotic and analgesic treatments. As an additional detoxifying, antihypoxic and tissue metabolism enhancing drug, 200 ml of Succinasol solution was infused 2 times a day into a maxillary vein. In order to compare the groups, leukocytosis level, leukocyte intoxication index (LII), wound debridement and tissue granulation level were calculated.*

Keywords: *acute paraproctitis, diabetes, complex treatment in paraproctitis, succinasol.*

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Relevance of the issue: According to statistical data, more than 537 million people (20-79 years old) suffer from diabetes. As an underlying disease, diabetes leads to severe complications in other illnesses, especially in purulent conditions.

Among the most common purulent surgical diseases, acute paraproctitis accounts for 0.5-4% of general surgical cases. In 5-58% of cases, acute paraproctitis presents in severe forms (ischioanal, perianal, retroanal, or horseshoe-shaped). In 4.0% of cases, the abscess ruptures into the abdominal cavity, and in 1.2% of cases, it spreads to the thigh and genital areas. In 24-88% of cases after surgery, recurrent paraproctitis or rectal fistula occurs. Anal sphincter insufficiency is observed in 6-27.9% of cases, and 17-36% of patients experience discomfort in the perianal area.

Depending on the location and severity of paraproctitis, either a radical or a two-stage operation is performed. In a radical operation, the purulent cavity is opened, sanitized, and the abscess tract and internal opening are removed. This method is used for mild cases of paraproctitis. In two-stage operations:

1. The purulent cavity is opened, sanitized, and the internal opening is ligature-drained. In the second stage, the fistula tract is excised.
2. The purulent cavity is opened and sanitized. In the second stage, the fistula tract is excised.

These methods are used for severe forms of paraproctitis.

In severe forms, wound healing is delayed due to the presence of purulent-necrotic tissues and generalized intoxication is observed. To reduce intoxication and accelerate wound healing, in addition to local antiseptic treatment and antibiotic therapy, the use of detoxification agents is advisable. Detoxification agents such as Reosorbilact, Succinazole, Sorbilact, and other saline infusion solutions are used. Succinazole contains succinic acid, a natural metabolite of the Krebs

cycle involved in cellular metabolism, which enhances ATP production. This, in turn, improves tissue microcirculation, promotes regeneration, and helps restore hemodynamics quickly.

Objective. Analyzing surgical tactics for acute paraproctitis in patients with diabetes and reducing general intoxication and accelerating wound healing through the use of the drug Succinazole.

Materials and Methods. A retrospective analysis was conducted on the medical histories of 42 patients with severe forms of acute paraproctitis treated in the Purulent Surgery Department of the Yakkasaroy District Medical Association in Tashkent from 2018 to 2020. Based on localization, 6 patients had the subcutaneous form with phlegmon in the thigh and scrotal areas. The ischiorectal form was observed in 26 patients, and the pelvirectal form in 10 patients. Four patients with the pelvirectal form and four with the ischiorectal form had coexisting diabetes. All patients presented with aerobic paraproctitis. Patients with subcutaneous and submucosal forms of the disease were not included in the study.

The patients observed were between 17 and 72 years old, with 28 males and 14 females. Six patients (14.3%) had previously undergone surgery for acute paraproctitis involving "opening of the purulent cavity." Among these, three had diabetes.

The patients were treated in the hospital for 3 to 11 days. Those with extended hospital stays primarily had acute pelvirectal paraproctitis and, to a lesser extent, acute ischiorectal paraproctitis. Wound healing was found to be slower in 8 patients with diabetes.

All patients underwent surgery to open and sanitize the purulent cavity under spinal anesthesia. During the postoperative period, local antiseptic treatment was applied 1-2 times daily.

The patients were divided into two main groups: a control group and a primary group. The control group of 20 patients received standard treatment, including daily local antiseptic care, antibiotics, and analgesics. In the primary group of 22 patients, Succinazole solution (200 ml) was additionally administered intravenously twice a day as a detoxifying, antihypoxic, and metabolic-enhancing agent.

To compare the groups, the level of leukocytosis, leukocyte intoxication index (LII), wound cleansing from pus, and degree of tissue granulation were evaluated.

The statistical results were obtained using the variation analysis method with the help of Microsoft Excel 2016 (Windows).

Results. The analysis shows that in patients with acute paraproctitis in the primary group, the level of leukocytosis decreased more quickly compared to the control group.

Table 1. Change in the level of leukocytosis in patients with acute paraproctitis over time.

Group	Days after the surgery		
	1	3	5
Examination	16,1 ±1,5	11,2 ±0,9	9,1 ±0,7
Main	15,4 ±1,6	9,3 ±0,8	7,4 ±0,7

In patients with acute paraproctitis, on the 1st day, the average LII was 3.8 ± 0.8 in the control group and 3.9 ± 0.8 in the primary group, with almost identical values. On the 3rd day, when the LII was recalculated, the control group had an average of 2.8 ± 0.4 , and the primary group had an average of 1.8 ± 0.3 , showing a more significant decrease in the primary group. By the 3rd day after surgery, some patients were discharged for outpatient care. On the 5th day, when the LII was calculated in patients who remained in the hospital, the control group had an average of 2.4 ± 0.4 , while the primary group had an average of 1.3 ± 0.5 , indicating a further reduction in the primary group.

Table 2. Change in the LII (Leukocyte Intoxication Index) over time in patients with acute paraproctitis.

Group	Days after the surgery		
	1	3	5
Examination	3,8±0,8	2,8±0,4	2,4±0,4
Main	3,9±0,8	1,8±0,3	1,3±0,5

In the control group, wound cleansing from pus and necrotic tissue was observed on average by the 4th to 5th day, while in the primary group, it began on average by the 3rd to 4th day. In the primary group, the wounds were completely cleansed of pus, and regeneration started more quickly compared to the control group.

Table 3. Wound healing stages in patients with acute paraproctitis.

Groups	Number of patients	Start of wound cleansing from pus	Complete cleansing of the wound from pus	Start of granulation in the wound
Examination	20	4-5 days	6-7 days	9-10 days
Main	22	3-4 days	5-6 days	7-8 days

Conclusion.

1. In patients with acute paraproctitis, a recurrence rate of 14.3% was identified. When considering complications associated with pararectal fistulas, the recurrence rate in acute paraproctitis is quite high. Therefore, it is advisable to use the radical method of "opening the purulent cavity and removing the internal opening" in cases of ischioanal, subcutaneous, and submucosal types of paraproctitis.
2. In patients with severe forms of acute paraproctitis, in addition to local antiseptic and systemic antibacterial treatment, the use of detoxifying, antihypoxic, and tissue metabolism-enhancing agent Succinazole improved the treatment effect. Under the influence of Succinazole, one of the signs of general intoxication, the Leukocyte Intoxication Index (LII), decreased, and the wound was cleansed of pus and necrotic tissue more quickly.

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